

Simultaneous determination of neodymium and erbium with 8-hydroxyquinoline and TX-100 by derivative spectrophotometry

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The absorption spectra of *4f* electron transitions of the neodymium and erbium complexes with 8-hydroxyquinoline in the presence of TX-100 have been studied by conventional and derivative spectra. The second derivative spectrum has been used to eliminate the interference of the other lanthanides and to increase the sensitivity by a further factor of 4–6. Beer's law is obeyed for 5–30 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Nd and Er. The relative standard derivations 1.1 and 1.0% for Nd and Er respectively. The detection limits, corresponding to a SNR of 2, are 0.12 and 0.10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for Nd and Er respectively. A method for the simultaneous determination of neodymium and erbium in mixed lanthanides has been proposed.

8-Hydroxyquinoline (HQ) has been widely employed for spectrophotometric/spectrofluorimetric determination of rare earth elements¹, but it has not been used for the determination of neodymium and erbium in the presence of others. In this work, we describe the complexes of Nd (or Er)-HQ in the presence of octylphenal poly(ethylene glycol)ether (TX-100) which are soluble in water, and their absorption bands of *4f* electron transitions are enhanced markedly². Use of the second derivative spectrum was found to eliminate the interference from the other rare earths and increased the sensitivity by a further factor of 4–6. On this basis, a method was developed for the simultaneous determination of neodymium and erbium in rare earth mixtures. The analytical results obtained are satisfactory.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of *4f* electron transitions of Nd(Er)-HQ complexes in the presence of TX-100, show that the band for the neodymium complex is shifted to longer wavelength compared to the spectrum of neodymium ion as chloride, and its resolution into three sharp bands centres at 572, 580 and 584 nm respectively, while that of the erbium complex is shifted to shorter wavelength (at 519 nm). The sensitivities were enhanced by a factor of 6–8.

The experimental results show that the conventional spectrophotometry for neodymium and erbium suffers from the interference by the background absorption of other lanthanide complexes. Therefore, in order to eliminate the interference, the first-to-fourth-derivative spectra of the complexes were investigated. On this basis, the second, derivative spectrum with $\lambda = 1.0$ nm, bandpass = 1.0 nm and scan rate = 20 nm min⁻¹ was chosen as it afforded the best sen-

sitivity. The optimal analytical signals are at 573.5 (+) and 517.5 (–) nm for Nd, and 516.0 (+) and 518.0 (–) nm for Er, where other lanthanide complexes produce no interference.

The chemical variables HQ, TX-100 and NaOH were optimized for 1.00×10^{-4} M of Nd and Er by varying one of them at a time and the results were as follows: 0.3–1.5 $\times 10^{-2}$ M HQ, 1.5–5.0% (w/v) TX-100 and 0.15–1.2 M NaOH. In the analysis of mixtures, the amount of HQ needed was found to be about 40 times that necessary for the sum of the lanthanides present. The complete complex formation required 5 min and the derivative absorptions were stable for at least 5 h.

Linear calibration graphs were obtained by plotting the amplitudes measured at 573.5 (+) and 571.5 (–) nm for Nd, and 516.0 (+) and 518.0 (–) nm for Er in the concentration range 5–30 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The detection limits, corresponding to a SNR of 2, were found to be 0.12 and 0.10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for Nd and Er respectively. The relative standard deviations (RSD) for ten successive determinations of 8.0 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Nd and Er were 1.1 and 1.0% respectively.

The procedure was applied to the determination of Nd in a reference material (from Baotou Rare Earths Academy, China; composition: La₂O₃, 27.11; CeO₂, 49.21; Pr₆O₁₁, 5.18; Nd₂O₃, 16.75; Sm₂O₃, 1.29; Eu₂O₃, 0.23; Gd₂O₃, 0.40; Tb₄O₇, 0.03; Dy₂O₃, 0.09; Y₂O₃, 0.27; Er₂O₃, 0.027; Ho₂O₃, 0.023; Tm₂O₃, 0.0085; Lu₂O₃, 0.003; Yb₂O₃, 0.013%) and the value was found to be 16.73% (average of five separate determinations), the certified value being 16.75%. The reference material was not available for Er. The applicability of the procedure to the determination of erbium in lanthanide mixtures was tested by adding 5.00% amounts of erbium in the above reference

material, and the results of average of five determinations, was found to be 4.96%.

Experimental

A Shimadzu UV-240 spectrophotometer with an Op 1-2 spectral processing attachment and 4.0 cm cells were used.

The standard solutions of lanthanides were prepared by dissolving their pure oxides (Johnson Matthey) in HCl and diluting with distilled water. A 0.20 M solution of 8-hydroxyquinoline (A.R., Shanghai Chemical Reagent Works, China), a 10% (w/v) solution of octylphenol poly(ethylene glycol)ether (TX-100, Rohm & Hass) and a 10.0 M NaOH were prepared in distilled water.

All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Procedure : A known volume of the lanthanide solution was mixed with solutions of HQ (2.50 ml) and TX-100 (4.0 ml) and NaOH (1.25 ml) solution and diluted to 10 ml with

distilled water. The second derivative spectrum was recorded against a reagent blank with 4.0 cm cells, $\Delta\lambda = 1.0$ nm, bandpass = 1.0 nm and scan rate = 20 nm min⁻¹. The amplitudes were measured between 573.5 (+) and 571.5 (-) nm for Nd, and 516.0 (+) and 518.0 (-) nm peaks for Er.

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